

Please cite as:

Azar, A., Khadivar, A., AMIN, N. M. R., & ANVARY, R. A. A. (2011). AN ARCHITECTURE FOR PERFORMANCE BASED BUDGETING WITH INTELLIGENT DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM APPROACH.
Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3352637

AN ARCHITECTURE FOR PERFORMANCE BASED BUDGETING WITH INTELLIGENT DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM APPROACH

AZAR ADEL*, KHADIVAR AMENEH, AMIN NASERI MODAMMAD REZA, ANVARY
ROSTAMY ALI ASGHAR

* DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT, FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT & ECONOMICS, TARBIAT MODARES
UNIVERSITY, TEHRAN, IRAN

Abstract:

This paper, first presents a literature review about the performance based budgeting and intelligent systems. Then the important factors in failure of budgeting systems relevant to the lack of intelligent system approach and the factors that make the process semi-structured are identified. The feasibility of using intelligent DSS approach for performance-based budgeting based on the expert's viewpoints is examined. The elements of the intelligent DSS_PBBS and their properties are identified: a fuzzy knowledge base, a linear programming model base, an object oriented database, a backward chaining, a data warehouse and user interface. At the end, the relationship between the elements and the architecture is presented and the results are compared with the other approaches.

Keyword(s): BUDGETING, PERFORMANCE-BASED BUDGETING, DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM, EXPERT SYSTEM